

JERUSALEM ARTICHOKE IS A SECONDARY RAW MATERIAL TO PRODUCE CONFECTIONERY PRODUCTS TARGETING PEOPLE WHO ARE ON A DIET

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Abstract: *This article shows the results of the chemical compositions of Jerusalem artichokes and the likelihood of applying it in the confectionery industry as a secondary raw material.*

Key words: *Jerusalem artichokes, Inulin, Starch, Dietary fiber*

Over the past years, scientists have put more emphasis on the creation of new ingredients and modern technologies to obtain new products in the production of dietary products. In this field, technologies for obtaining products based on the dietary component of inulin-containing nodular plants, which include Jerusalem artichoke, have been created. Scientific research is being carried out to obtain high-quality products to preserve the biological value of the manufactured products, and to make effective use of natural raw materials and products. In the last a couple of decades, a lot of progress has been made in the processing of agricultural and vegetable products which led to some breakthroughs on the creation of new technologies in the field of storage and processing of vegetable products. Now, a diet based on fruits and vegetables and the technologies of deriving vitamin-rich products are on the agenda. Therefore, it is important to select carbohydrate-rich plants, isolate carbohydrates, and use natural sugar substitutes instead of sugar, and channel them to the production of dietary food products.

So far, Rakhimov, S. Kh, E.G. Afrikyan, Yu.R. Akopyan, M.G. Kholyavka, M.N. Nazarenko, D.A have done scientific research into processing of plant raw materials. As a result, this, in turn, caused the creation of plant processing technologies, and the development of deriving inulin extract with the focus on purification.

Nailya Z. Dubkova, Vitaly V. Kharkov, Marcel R. Vakhitov have put forward the following new method in their long-term scientific research work: "Artichoke is a valuable low-maintenance crop, its roots contain important nutrients and prebiotics. We propose the use of Jerusalem artichoke powder as a functional nutrient in food production."

LA. Reshetnik, OV Prokopiev, and NK Kochnev conducted fascinating research on Jerusalem artichoke and came to the following conclusion: "Currently, more attention is paid to natural medicines. Jerusalem artichoke has a special place among them. This plant is distinguished by its unique chemical composition (a large amount of inulin and fructan, a protein consisting of essential 8 amino acids, the presence of a rich vitamin and mineral composition), which allows to obtain medicine for the treatment and prevention of various diseases. .

Jerusalem artichoke is a unique agricultural crop, because of its above-ground and root parts are useful. In addition, Jerusalem artichoke is one of the highest yielders in the world: up to 200 t/ha of green mass and 150 t/ha of roots. It is the only cultural plant that does not require a lot of labor and constant care.

Jerusalem artichoke is an intensive plant capable of absorbing carbon from the air and releasing oxygen: 1 ha Jerusalem artichoke can absorb 6 tons of carbon dioxide gas per year, and 1 ha forest can absorb 3-4 tons of carbon dioxide gas. Planting artichokes around manufacturing plants can be an effective way to prevent air pollution. Jerusalem artichoke accumulates less nitrates, heavy metals and radionuclides than other plants.

The chemical composition of Jerusalem artichoke changes depending on the geographical factor, biological characteristics of the variety and soil-climatic conditions, including agricultural technology, weather conditions in a certain growing year. Jerusalem artichoke contains 19-30% dry matter. The average chemical composition of Jerusalem artichoke is given in Table 1.

Jerusalem artichoke contains a complex of unique carbohydrates based on fructose and its polymers, the highest homolog of which is inulin, the most valuable and quantitatively superior carbohydrate component. It is mainly found in Jerusalem artichokes with sugar up to 13-20%. The chemical composition of the carbon complex in Jerusalem artichoke is presented in Table 2.

Jerusalem artichoke contains a high amount of silicon, which is important for human metabolic processes. A high content of iron salts was found in Jerusalem artichoke, which is about 3 times higher than the content of iron in other root crops. In terms of magnesium, iron, silicon, zinc, as well as vitamins B and C, Jerusalem artichoke is superior

to potatoes, carrots and beets. Jerusalem artichoke has a unique ability to accumulate a high amount of inulin, which is broken down into fructose in the human body, which is necessary for people with diabetes. Products containing Jerusalem artichoke perfectly meet the scientifically based requirements for the diet of a modern person who has a sedentary lifestyle (lack of exercise) in conditions of poor ecology and psychological overload.

Jerusalem artichoke is a crop that is used for various purposes. Its production areas, product types and areas of application are presented in Table 5.

Table 1.

Chemical composition of Jerusalem artichoke

Substances	Jerusalem artichoke (content %)	
	At the node	Above ground
Water	77.5	70.5
Dry matter	22.5	29.5
Sugar	16.9	4.0
Cellulose	1.9	10.9
Fat	0.1	3.4
Protein	2.3	2.2
Dietary fiber	3.5	6.4

Table 2.

Chemical composition of the carbohydrate complex contained in Jerusalem artichoke

Substances	Content	
	% by wet weight	% by dry weight
Inulin	11-21	51.8-72.4
Starch	0.1-0.4	0.27-1.38
Hemicellulose	1.0-3.0	3.43-10.3
Cellulose	1.1-3.0	3.41-10.3
Monose	0.1-2.5	0.34-8.6

Jerusalem artichoke green mass serves as a source for obtaining raw materials for the production of fructose-glucose syrup, potassium,

magnesium, calcium, etc. The composition and dry green mass of Jerusalem artichoke are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

Jerusalem artichoke dry green mass composition %

Jerusalem artichoke sort	Crude protein	Crude cellulose	Fat	Ash	Ca	K	Mg
Skorospelka	20.0	13.4	3.6	11.4	1.80	2.75	0.56
Nakhotka	21.3	12.5	4.5	12.1	1.96	2.70	0.65
Novost VIRa	19.1	12.5	3.6	12.5	1.77	2.73	0.51

Table 4.

Jerusalem artichoke protein amine content %

Raw material	Amino acid composition, % by mass									
	Protein	Lysine	Histidine	Arginine	Threonine	Valine	Phenylalanine	Leucine	Tryptophan	Tyrosine
The green part of Jerusalem artichoke	11.52	0.46	1	1.02	0.53	1.06	0.38	2.11	2.12	0.13
Jerusalem artichoke Nodule	8.83	0.33	0.22	0.46	0.3	1.33	0.48	0.85	0.82	0.12

Areas of using Jerusalem artichoke

National economic networks	Products	Area of use
In agriculture	Fodder and feed additives, veterinary drugs	animal husbandry, Veterinary medicine
Food industry	In the preparation of bread, pasta, confectionery, tea and coffee, soft drinks,	Restaurants, home cooking
	Dry drinks and extracts, kvass, fructose-glucose syrups, sucats, diet puree	Diet therapy
	Dry drinks and extracts, kvass, fructose-glucose syrups, sucats, diet puree, jam, tablets	Functional health nutrition
	Jam, tablets, yogurt, cottage cheese	Preventive baby food
In medicine	Medical and medical-prophylactic drugs	Traditional folk medicine
	Injection forms, capsules, degrees, powders	New generation immunological preparations
	Inulin; tablets, capsules, phytocomposition preparations containing	Taking pectin, bacterial preparations (bifidum and lactobacterium)

	Jerusalem artichoke for therapeutic baths	
In the cosmetics industry	Cosmetic products	Therapeutic and preventive cosmetics
Bioenergy	Ethyl alcohol (bioethanol, butanol)	Motor fuel for internal combustion engine
Electrical industry	Hydroxymethylfurfural	Light-emitting diodes, LEDs, semiconductors, photoconductors, liquid crystals, photochromic and other materials.
Biotechnology industry	Carbon fibers, nanocellulose	Composite materials
Environmental protection	Jerusalem artichoke plant	Purification of polluted air

To sum up, the results of the research allow us to make the following conclusions:

1. To study the composition of mineral substances in Jerusalem artichoke
2. Fields of use of Jerusalem artichoke were studied.
3. Jerusalem artichoke powder developed for obtaining high-quality bakery products in the food industry is recommended.

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